

Prospective observational study of hyperlactataemia in elective tumour craniotomy – short statistical analysis plan.

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Introduction

Although hyperlactataemia is common in patients undergoing elective tumour craniotomy, the prevalence, clinical significance, and pathophysiology are debated. The reported prevalence ranges from 32% to 68%¹⁻¹⁰ and factors such as tumour characteristics, comorbidity, glucocorticoids, and surgery-related variables seem to contribute. While elevated blood lactate is associated with severity and poor prognosis in critically ill patients¹¹, its impact on outcomes in brain tumour craniotomy remains uncertain. Some studies link hyperlactatemia to prolonged hospital stay^{3,8,10}, neurological deficits⁵, and 30-day mortality⁷, while others find no significant associations^{1,6,9}. Most studies are retrospective^{1,3,5-7,10}, with only two prospective studies^{8,9} available. A systematic review and meta-analysis¹² was performed on five of the studies^{3,5,8-10}. It reported no association with development of new neurological deficits, duration of hospitalization, mortality at 30 days and survival at 6 months.

Here, we present a statistical analysis plan for a prospective cohort study with the aim to investigate hyperlactataemia prevalence and risk factors in elective tumour craniotomy, as well as its association with changes in neurological disability (modified Rankin Scale and new neurological deficits), length of hospital stay, and 30-day mortality.

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Methods

The study adheres to the Helsinki Declaration and ICMJE Recommendations for the Protection of Research Participants. The study protocol was published ¹³, approved by the Scientific-Ethics Committee of the Capital Region in Denmark (identifier: H-20011650; 21 July 2020), the Danish Data Protection Agency (identifier: P-2020-566; 18 May 2020) and registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (identifier: NCT04410315; 14 May 2020). The study will be reported in accordance with the "Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology" (STROBE) guidelines.

Participants

Inclusion criteria:

Patients with (1) full mental capacity, aged 18 years or older, and scheduled for elective brain tumour craniotomy, (2) who comprehend both written and spoken Danish.

Exclusion criteria:

Patients (1) scheduled for stereotactic biopsy or pituitary surgery, (2) previously enrolled in the study, or (3) those unable to provide written informed consent.

Standard care and intervention

All participants received standard clinical treatment, supplemented by additional blood sampling from the radial artery (where a catheter was inserted as part of perioperative monitoring) and two standardized neurological disability assessments, one before surgery and one 30 days after surgery (over telephone), using the modified Rankin Scale (mRS).

Measurements

Blood was drawn at first incision and once hourly thereafter until the patients had been observed for six hours in the Post Anaesthesia Care Unit. The blood was analysed using a point-of-care ABL800 FLEX blood gas analyser (Radiometer Medical, Denmark).

Data management

Blood sample data was electronically extracted from the hospital's medical record system (Sundhedsplatformen, Epic Systems Corporation, USA), while clinical data was manually entered into

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Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap, Vanderbilt University, Nashville, USA) hosted at Region Hovedstaden, Denmark.

Terminology

Existing studies on hyperlactataemia in tumour craniotomy have used different definitions, with most setting the threshold at ≥ 2.0 mM or at > 2.0 mM. We set the threshold at serum lactate ≥ 2.2 mM, consistent with the study from Brallier et al.⁵ from which we calculated our sample size. Participants were grouped as being normolactataemic or hyperlactataemic based on their maximal lactate value.

Hyperlactataemia is defined as at least one measurement of serum lactate ≥ 2.2 mM within the observation period. Lactate load is defined as the area under the curve of serum lactate from the time of incision until last measurement in the PACU divided by time (hours); while lactate burden is defined by area under the curve of serum lactate above 2.2 mmol/L from the time of incision until the last measurement in the PACU. We will further compare the strength of the crude association between these measures of hyperlactataemia and the primary outcome by survival analysis after grouping each lactate measure by quartiles and select the variable with the strongest association as the one to be used for primary analyses.

Outcomes

Primary outcome:

- Change in mRS from preoperative assessment to 30 days after surgery.*

Secondary outcomes:

- Length of hospital stay from day of surgery to discharge (days).*
- Mortality at 30 days.*
- Days alive and out of hospital at 30 days.**
- New neurological deficits at discharge. ***

*These endpoints were predetermined in our published protocol¹³.

**Recognizing the growing use of the patient-centred outcome "days alive and out of hospital" in perioperative research, we chose to add it as a secondary outcome in the final analysis¹⁴.

***We chose to include the onset of new neurological deficits at discharge as a secondary outcome (defined as an exploratory outcome in our protocol) to directly compare our findings with those of Brallier et al.

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Identification of confounders

To guide adjustments in our statistical models, we used causal directed acyclic graphs¹⁵ to identify instruments, confounders, competing exposures, mediators, and colliders amongst our predefined exploratory variables¹³.

Instruments = ancestors of the exposure (hyperlactataemia)

- Glucocorticoid treatment pre- or intraoperatively
- Blood gas parameter: glucose
- Fluid therapy with Ringer-lactate
- Positioning during surgery (prone, supine or lateral)
- Vasopressor total intraoperative dose (ephedrine, noradrenaline or metaxedrine)
- Type of anaesthesia (TIVA, sevoflurane, awake craniotomy)

Confounders = ancestors of the exposure (hyperlactataemia) and outcome (Δ mRS)

- BMI
- Blood loss
- Blood gas parameter: PaO₂
- Charlson Comorbidity Score (includes age, liver disease, kidney disease and diabetes mellitus)
- Complete/incomplete resection
- Hypotension
- Preoperative chemo/radiation/immunotherapy
- Surgery duration
- Surgery events/complications
- Tumour type, size and location

Competing exposures = ancestors of outcome (Δ mRS)

- Mobilization in PACU (no mobilization, mobilization to upright sitting or to standing/out of bed)
- Postoperative nausea, vomiting and pain

We did not identify any colliders (descendants of both exposure and outcome) or mediators (descendants of exposure and ancestors of outcome) amongst our variables. Fluid therapy with isotonic NaCl, diuresis, blood transfusion and blood gas parameters such as pH, PaCO₂, Na⁺, K⁺ and Cl⁻ should not have any impact on the exposure or the outcome. The directed acyclic graphs are shown in Figure 1.

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In addition to the variables defined in the protocol and characterized with the help of directed acyclic graphs, the author group has discussed the role of preoperative mRS. One could argue that preoperative mRS itself predicts Δ mRS, and that patients with high preoperative mRS have a higher risk of change in Δ mRS. It could therefore be considered as a competing exposure.

Figure 1. A visualization of causal directed acyclic graphs.

The exposure, hyperlactataemia, marked in green (▶) and the outcome, change in mRS, marked in blue (I). Instruments in green, confounders in pink, competing exposures in blue and variables not affecting the exposure or the outcome in white.

Sample size

The sample size was calculated based on the study by Brallier et al⁵, who observed a 15% incidence of new neurological deficits in patients with S-lactate \geq 2.2 mmol/L, as opposed to 7% in patients with S-lactate $<$ 2.2 mmol/L. A standardized difference of 0.26 was calculated from the two groups¹⁶. With an assumed

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power of 0.8 and a significance level of 0.05, and using a graphical approximation¹⁷, we arrived at the sample size of 450 patients.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis will be carried out in close collaboration between two investigators using the latest stable version of R (R Core Team, Vienna, Austria).

Descriptive statistics

All data will be presented as mean and 95% confidence intervals if a normal distribution can be assumed, if this is not the case, we will use median and interquartile range. Dichotomous demographic data will be presented as number and percentage.

Prevalence

The prevalence of hyperlactataemia will be calculated as a percentage of patients with one measurement of serum lactate ≥ 2.2 mM within the observation period.

Association to outcome

Alpha level of 0.05 will be used for our primary outcome. The secondary analyses are considered hypothesis-generating and exploratory. The outcome analyses are outlined in Table 1. Lactate will be analysed as a binary variable (serum lactate above and below 2.2 mmol/L) and as a continuous variable (calculating total lactate load and lactate burden), as described in "Terminology". Δ mRS, length of stay and days alive and out of hospital will be analysed using two different multivariate regression models. In one model, we will adjust for a marker of preoperative health (Charlson Comorbidity Score), intracranial status (tumour type) and an intraoperative marker (noradrenaline dose). In the second model we will use a backward stepwise regression approach, beginning with a saturated model that will include all identified confounders mentioned in "Identification of confounders". We have defined our stopping rule or Alpha-to-Remove as 0.1. Once a variable is out of the model, it is not allowed back. The process will be repeated until either all variables are out of the model, or no variable meets the criteria defined by the stopping rule. For mortality, in addition to the two regression models mentioned above, we will explore crude survival with the help of a simple logistic regression without any adjustments. We will also attempt to reproduce the results of Brallier et al. who investigated the association between dichotomous lactate and new neurological deficits with a Multivariate Logistic Regression adjusted for sex, age, BMI, surgical time, Risk Stratification Index (RSI) for in-hospital mortality¹⁸, tumour location.

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Table 1: Statistical Analysis Plan for Hyperlactatemia's Association with Primary and Secondary Outcomes.	
<p><u>Dichotomous lactate</u> and ΔmRS (0-30 d)*</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Multivariate Linear Regression adjusted for Charlson comorbidity score, tumour type and intraoperative noradrenaline dose. 2) Multivariate Linear Backward Stepwise Regression 	<p><u>Continuous lactate</u> and ΔmRS (0-30 d)*</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Multivariate Linear Regression adjusted for Charlson comorbidity score, tumour type and intraoperative noradrenaline dose. 2) Multivariate Linear Backward Stepwise Regression
<p><u>Dichotomous lactate</u> and LOS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Multivariate Linear Regression adjusted for Charlson comorbidity score, tumour type and intraoperative noradrenaline dose. 2) Multivariate Linear Backward Stepwise Regression 	<p><u>Continuous lactate</u> and LOS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Multivariate Linear Regression adjusted for Charlson comorbidity score, tumour type and intraoperative noradrenaline dose. 2) Multivariate Linear Backward Stepwise Regression
<p><u>Dichotomous lactate</u> and alive and OOH 30 d</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Multivariate Linear Regression adjusted for Charlson comorbidity score, tumour type and intraoperative noradrenaline dose. 2) Multivariate Linear Backward Stepwise Regression 	<p><u>Continuous lactate</u> and alive and OOH 30 d</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Multivariate Linear Regression adjusted for Charlson comorbidity score, tumour type and intraoperative noradrenaline dose. 2) Multivariate Linear Backward Stepwise Regression
<p><u>Dichotomous lactate</u> and mortality 30 d</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Multivariate Logistic Regression adjusted for Charlson comorbidity score, tumour type and intraoperative noradrenaline dose. 2) Multivariate Logistic Backward Stepwise Regression 3) Crude survival: Simple Logistic Regression without adjustments 	<p><u>Continuous lactate</u> and mortality 30 d</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Multivariate Logistic Regression adjusted for Charlson comorbidity score, tumour type and intraoperative noradrenaline dose. 2) Multivariate Logistic Backward Stepwise Regression 3) Crude survival: Simple Logistic Regression without adjustments
<p><u>Dichotomous lactate</u> and new neurological deficits at discharge</p> <p>Reproducing the findings of Brallier et al. who used a Multivariate Logistic Regression adjusted for sex, age, BMI, surgical time, Risk Stratification Index (RSI) for in-hospital mortality, tumour location.</p>	
<p>* Primary outcome analysis</p>	

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Risk factors for hyperlactataemia

For identifying risk factors for developing hyperlactataemia, we will use a multivariate backward stepwise regression approach. Starting with a saturated model that will include all identified variables (listed as instruments and confounders in “Identification of confounders”), we will remove variables based on p values, in a stepwise manner until there are no variables left to remove. We will remove one variable at a time being the one with the highest p-value. The p-value for removal will be set at 0.1.

Missing data

Several factors could contribute to missing data in our dataset.

- 1) Blood samples: may be absent due to issues such as catheter clots, malfunctions of the blood gas analysing equipment, or the unavailability of personnel to collect samples. The missing blood samples are therefore most likely missing at random.
- 2) Functional outcome assessments (Δ mRS): if patients can not be reached 30 days after surgery, functional outcome assessment by modified Rankin Scale will be missing. These data are most likely not missing at random, as patients with worse functional outcome are more likely to miss their assessment. We will address missing data by providing the number of missing mRS follow-ups.
- 3) Alive and out of hospital: if patients moved to another region (e.g. Greenland or Faroe Islands), data of readmission to hospital might be missing. These data are not missing at random. However, the number of patients moving back to Greenland or Faroe Islands are expected to be few (less than 2%). If the reason for readmission is neurosurgical or severe in nature, they will be readmitted to Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark.
- 4) New neurological deficits: due to variability among clinicians, we assume that some new neurological deficits might be overlooked or not noted in the patient journal. These data are assumed to be missing at random.
- 5) Length of hospital stay and mortality: we assume no missing data here, as these data are registered automatically in the electronic patient journal and the Danish Death Registry.

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